

A Review on Blood Coagulation Factors

Roohullah Arifzai ✉

Department of Biology, Sayed Jamaluddin Afghani University, Kunar City, Kunar, Afghanistan

Sheeraz Khan Rasheedy

Department of Chemistry, Sayed Jamaluddin Afghani University, Kunar City, Kunar, Afghanistan

Abstract

This article is an analysis of the clotting factors. The coagulation cascade is a well-studied and pertinent topic that is crucial for health professionals to understand. Although this article does not cover the coagulation cascade and its role in hemostasis as a simple chain of events, a brief overview will be included. coagulation is a natural process that occurs to prevent bleeding vascular damage, but if this process is formed abnormally, various diseases can occur as a result of this disorder. More than 50 different substances that have an effect on blood coagulation have been found in blood and tissues, some of them are known as procoagulant substances and some of them are known as anticoagulant substances. Blood clotting or not depends on the balance between these two groups of substances. Normally, anticoagulants are dominant and blood does not coagulate, but when a vein ruptures, coagulants are activated in the area of damage and overwhelm the anticoagulants, and then a blood clot. A systematic search was conducted across several academic databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, HighWire, MD Consult, and Scopus. Following a rigorous screening process, 19 relevant articles were selected for inclusion in this study. The findings demonstrate that coagulation factors a group of plasma proteins interact with platelets to promote hemostasis and blood clot formation. Among these, 13 essential coagulation factors have been identified, which undergo sequential activation and complex interactions to drive the coagulation cascade, ensuring effective clot formation at sites of vascular injury.

Keywords: *coagulation, fibrinogen, Prothrombin, proaccelerin.*

Suggested citation: Arifzai, R., & Rasheedy, S.K. (2025). A Review on Blood Coagulation Factors. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(9), 1-9. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2025.2(9).01

Introduction

When someone is injured, a procedure called blood coagulation is used to stop blood loss. In the area of the wound, the blood coagulates and forms a barrier that stops bleeding. One of the most significant and essential physiological functions in the human body, blood coagulation is influenced by a wide range of circumstances. According to Elyasi et al. (2018), a number of congenital and acquired deficiencies in each of these components might impact the coagulation process and result in several issues for people.

Coagulation factors are a family of highly glycosylated plasma proteins. And most of them except (F1 and FII) are available in very small concentrations. These factors, except tissue factor (TF) are bound to plasma membrane proteins and require a proteolytic activation step (Naderi, & Naji

2017). Some of the coagulation factors are dependent on vitamin K and carboxylation occurs in their glutamic acid side chains by enzymatic reactions. Except for γ -carboxylation, other post-translational changes such as phosphorylation, sulfation and addition of β -hydroxyaspartic acid are seen in other coagulation factors (Elyasi, et al., 2018).

Perhaps the most important and fundamental elements of hemostasis are clotting factors. The body's physiological reaction to vascular endothelial damage is called hemostasis, and it causes a number of procedures that try to keep blood in the vascular system by forming a clot (Barmore et al., 2023). Coagulation protein nomenclature is fairly complicated. The terms fibrinogen, prothrombin, tissue factor (TF), and calcium are the popular designations for the first four of the twelve factors that were initially identified (Barnoyev, 2023). Roman numbers have not been given to the more recently identified clotting factors, high-molecular-weight kininogen and prekallikrein. Because of their short-lived coagulant activity in preserved blood, factors V and VIII are sometimes known as the labile factors (Caldwell et al., 2006).

Table 1. Coagulation Factors

Symbol	Names	Cofactor(s)	Plasma half life(h)	Plasma Concentration (nM)	Vi.K Dependent
FI	Fibrinogen	Ca ⁺⁺	64-96	8800	–
FII	Prothrombin	Ca	48	1400	+
FV	Proaccelerin	Ca.PL	12	20	+
FVII	Procovertin	TF.Ca.PL	4-6	10	+
FVIII	Antihaemophilic globulin A	Ca.PL	15-20	0,7 (Blood group dependent)	–
FIX	Antihaemophilic Factor B Christmas Factor	Ca.F VIIIa.PL	24	90	+
FX	Stuart- Prower – Factor	Ca.Fva.PL	32	170	+
FXI	Plasma Thromboplastin anteceden	Ca.PL negatively charged surfaces	40-80	30	–
FXII	Hagemann Factor	negatively charged surfaces	50-70	400	–
FXIII	Fibrin stabilizing Factor, Plasma transglutaminase	Fibrin,CA	40-50	50	–
TF	Tissue Factor	PL,Ca membrane		–	–
PK	Prekallikrein	negatively charged surfaces		400	–
HMWK (orHK)	High Molecular Weight Kininogen	negatively charged surfaces		700	–

Source: Caldwell, et al 2006

Methodology

Related articles were searched from Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, High Wire, MD Consult and Scopus data bases. Forty-six articles were chosen for this research, but after primary

screening some articles were eliminated due to duplication and irrelevant content. Finally, after another revision, 19 articles were included in the study.

Coagulation Factor I or Fibrinogen

It is a plasma-soluble glycoprotein that is converted into fibrin strands in the coagulation cascade by thrombin (Barzian, & Rezvani, 2023). Also, by binding to GpIIb/IIIa receptors in platelets, it plays a role in connecting them together like a bridge. This 340 kilodalton protein is made in the liver and can be measured in plasma with a concentration of about 1.5 to 3 grams per liter. During the normal process of blood coagulation, the strands of this soluble protein are converted into the insoluble form of fibrin, which results in the formation of a network form due to the effect of factor XIII (Gobel, etal 2018).

Higher amounts of fibrinogen are seen in patients with cardiovascular diseases. An increase in fibrinogen can also be seen in inflammations such as gum disease. In pregnancy, the amount of fibrinogen increases up to 4.5 grams per liter. On the other hand, the decrease in the amount of fibrinogen can be an evidence of the increase in the function of the coagulation system, which is caused by the consumption of this factor more than its production, and this is the situation that is observed in cases of Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation (Mashayekhi & Shahbazi 2014).

Coagulation Factor II or Prothrombin

Prothrombin is one of the plasma proteins that is present in normal plasma with a concentration of about 15 mg/dL (Hall, & Guyton, 2010). Prothrombin is an unstable protein that can be easily broken down into smaller compounds, one of which is thrombin with a molecular weight of 36,000 daltons, which is almost half the molecular weight of prothrombin (Hall, & Guyton, 2010). Prothrombin is continuously formed by the liver and is continuously used throughout the body for blood clotting (Gobel, etal 2018).

When the liver cannot produce prothrombin, its concentration in the plasma decreases so much within one to several days that it is unable to cause normal blood coagulation. The liver needs vitamin K for the normal formation of prothrombin and four other coagulation factors. Therefore, the lack of vitamin K or the presence of a liver disease that prevents the normal formation of prothrombin can reduce the concentration of prothrombin to such low levels that the tendency to bleed occurs (Hall, & Guyton, 2010). Activation of prothrombin to mature and transform into thrombin occurs by the activity of the prothrombinase proteolytic complex, which includes a serine proteinase factor Xa, factor V cofactors, Ca^{+2} ions, and phospholipids (Joseph, & Kini, 2004). Thrombin is a serine protease enzyme that is active in the blood coagulation process (Joseph, & Kini, 2004). Thrombin is the product of prothrombin protein (coagulation factor II) and active thrombin converts soluble fibrinogen into insoluble fibrin in the process of blood clotting (Nelson & Cox 2005).

Coagulation Factor III Tissue Thromboplastin

Tissue factor, which is the main initiator of the coagulation cascade, is found in the tissue under the endothelium of blood vessels and white blood cells. In the blood coagulation cycle, this protein is necessary for the formation of thrombin from prothrombin. As a result of vascular wall injuries, tissue factor enters the vascular system and in the presence of calcium ions, it activates factor VII,

and finally the complex of these two factors activates factor X. Prothrombin time (PT) is the test to evaluate this stage and factors I, II, V, VII, X (Nelson, & Cox, 2005).

Coagulation Factor IV or Calcium Ions

Calcium ions are necessary for all reactions of the coagulation cascade except for the activation of factor XII and XI. In the absence of calcium ions, blood does not clot, so precipitating or dissolving calcium ions with ethylenediminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) is a way to keep blood outside the body without causing clots (Schenone, et al, 2004).

Coagulation Factor V or Proaccelerin

Factor V is a protein in the coagulation system that acts as a cofactor. Signs and symptoms of factor V deficiency can begin at any age, although in most severe cases symptoms appear in childhood. A deficiency in factor V usually causes epistaxis, subcutaneous bleeding, necrotizing blood, rapid bruising, bleeding gums, and heavy and prolonged bleeding after surgery, injury, or pregnancy. Women with factor V deficiency may have heavy and continuous menstrual bleeding. Factor V deficiency affects approximately one person in every one million people, in countries such as Iran, southern India, and the Jewish population of the world, due to the high number of consanguineous marriages, this rate is much higher than in Western countries (Dall'Osso, et al, 2008).

Coagulation Factor VI or Platelets

Platelets play a role in blood coagulation and in preventing blood vessel bleeding by forming a platelet mass and helping to repair the vessel wall. Factors that cause platelets to stick to each other and form a clot include: activation of platelets and release, which facilitates the formation of glycoprotein and phospholipoprotein complexes on the membrane of two adjacent platelets. Also, the production of TXA₂, which originates from arachidic acid released from membrane phospholipids, causes clot formation. At the cut site, the clot formed by von Willebrand factor or fibronectins adheres to sub endothelial collagen fibers and prevents bleeding by forming a hemostasis stopper. Platelets facilitate coagulation reactions by releasing some coagulation factors such as factors V, I, and VII, and for this reason, they are also called thrombocytes. The decrease in the number of platelets is called thrombocytopenia, which is associated with blood coagulation disorders. In this regard, the release of heparin-neutralizing proteins such as Platelet factor4 and TG intensifies clot formation at the incision site and finally participates in clot contraction. On the other hand, from the breaking of platelets, a substance called serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine) is released into the blood, which has vasoconstriction properties (Homayounfar 1996).

Coagulation Factor VII or Proconvertin

Factor seven is a glycoprotein dependent on vitamin K, which has 406 amino acids and a molecular weight of 50 kilo Daltons. Factor seven circulates in plasma in two forms. Most of it is inactive single-chain zymogen and a small percentage is active double-chain with heavy and light chains. The conversion of factor seven into the active form (FVIIa) is done by breaking the peptide bond between amino acids isoleucine number 153 and Arginine number 152 (Perry, 2002).

Factor seven plays a central role in the initiation of coagulation, when blood vessels are damaged, factor seven binds to tissue factor (TF) on the surface of damaged cells and is activated. TF/FVIIa complex activates a small amount of factors X and IX, and active factor X (FXa) combined with FVa converts a limited amount of prothrombin to thrombin. Then thrombin platelets activate FV and FVIII. The final step that happens on the platelets, the complex including active FIX, active FVIII, calcium and acidic phospholipids convert more FX to Fxa, which leads to clot formation (Lau, 2003).

Coagulation Factor VIII or Ant Hemophilic Factor

Factor VIII is a plasma glycoprotein that acts as a cofactor for serine protease activity of active factor IX and in the conversion of inactive factor X to active factor X. a mutation or defect in coagulation factor FVIII is the most common form of blood disorder, occurring in one in 5,000 men and one in 10,000 women (Franchini & Mannucci, 2010).

Factor IX or Plasma Thromboplastin Component

Human factor IX is a blood coagulation factor the functional defect or hereditary absence causes hemophilia B (CHRISTMAS) disease. The mature factor IX is a single-chain glycoprotein with a length of 415 amino acids and a molecular weight of about 57 kilo Daltons (Biron, et al., 1999), which is obtained from the processing of the pro-factor IX protein with 461 amino acids. The factor IX is Like coagulation factors VII, X, prothrombin, protein Z, C, and S Vitamin K-dependent proteins (VKD) that require post-translational modifications, including gamma carboxylation, for their biological function. The propeptide in these proteins contains the recognition sequence of the gamma carboxylase enzyme (Roberts, 1993), and the gamma carboxylase, by binding to the 18-amino acid propeptide sequence on VKD proteins, converts specific glutamic acids into glutamic acid gamma carboxyl residues (Hassanabadi & Moghadam, 2018).

Coagulation Factor X Stuart-Prower Factor

Coagulation factor X is a vitamin K-dependent protein that belongs to the family of serine proteases and thus plays an essential role in blood coagulation. This factor is made in the liver as a single chain. In plasma, factor X is a double-chain glycoprotein. The light chain is separated from the heavy chain during or after secretion into the bloodstream. This factor contains 306 amino acid residues in the heavy chain and 139 amino acid residues in the light chain (Fatafta, et al., 2021), which are connected through a disulfide bond (Persson, et al 1989).

Activation of factor X by external complex includes TF-VIIa complex, phospholipid membrane and calcium ions. The internal complex of activation factorX includes the FVIIIa/FXa complex and phospholipid which converts prothrombin to thrombin. Deficiency of Factor X causes severe bleeding disorders (Kalantarian, et al 2015).

Coagulation Factor XI or Plasma Thromboplastin Antecedent

Coagulation factor eleven is a plasma glycoprotein that plays an important role in blood coagulation. Factor 11 is made in the liver and therefore the level of factor XI is lower in people with liver diseases. Deficiency of Coagulation factor 11 is an autosomal genetic defect that also

known as hemophilia C and Rosenthal syndrome, and it leads to mild to moderate bleeding in affected patients. This disease is seen in both males and females with the same ratio (Minnema et al 1999). The prevalence deficiency of factor eleven among the non-Jewish population is reported to be about one in a million. Cases of bleeding that have been reported in deficiency of factor 11 patients in different parts of the body include joint bleeding and brain bleeding (Bolton-Maggs, 1998).

Coagulation Factor XII or Hageman Factor

Factor XII is made in the liver and has a half-life of 40-50 hours. This factor is activated by contact with the external surface. Factor XII plays a role in the internal pathway of coagulation and fibrinolysis system. Deficiency of factor XII is assessed by prolonging the relative time of activated thromboplastin. the Acquired deficiency of factor XII is related to liver disease, nephritic syndrome and chronic granulocytic leukemia. Full-term newborns and healthy premature babies have 15-20% factor XII of adults. However, in children over 3 months, the activity levels of factor XII reach the values of adults (Butenas & Mann, 2015).

Coagulation Factor XIII or Fibrin-Stabilizing Factor

Coagulation factor XIII is a proenzyme that has transglutaminase properties in its active state. This factor acts in the last part of the coagulation cascade and the fibrin clot without covalent bonds turns into a stable fibrin clot by the action of this enzyme. With this action, fibrin becomes resistant to plasmin. Coagulation factor XIII is formed from two subunits A and B in the form of a tetrad (A2B2). These two subunits are coded by separate genes (Ichinose, et al 2005). Deficiency of factor XIII causes the fibrin clot to be unstable at the end of the coagulation process and is easily broken down by the fibrinolytic system, and it causes significant clinical symptoms such as cerebral hemorrhage, delayed bleeding, frequent miscarriages, and delay in healing and wound healing for the patient (Naderi, et al 2013).

Table 2. Characteristics of Coagulation Factors

Coagulation factor deficiency	Inheritance	Hemostatic level	laboratory disorder			Prevalence in the population	Treatment	Plasma half-life
			TT	PT	aPTT			
Fibrinogen	AR	mg/dl 100	+	+	+	1 in 1,000,000	Cryoprecipitate	2-4d
Prothrombin	AR	20-30%	-	+	+	1 in 2,000,000	FFP/PCCs	3-4d
Proaccelerin	AR	٪٢٠-١٥	-	+/-	+/-	1 in 2,000,000	FFP	36h
Proconvertin	AR	15-20%	-	+	-	1 in 5,000,00	FFP/PCCs	4-6h
Ant-hemophilic Factor A	dependent on X	30%	-	-	+	1 in 5,000	Concentrate	8-12h
Anti-hemophilic Factor B	dependent on X	30%	-	-	+	1 in 3,0000	Concentrate	8-24h
Stuart- Prower – Factor	AR	15-20%	-	+/-	+/-	1 in 1,000,000	FFP/PCCs	40-60h

Plasma Thromboplastin antecedent	AR	15-20%	-	-	+	1 in 1,000,000	FFP	40-70h
Hageman Factor	AR	B	-	-	+	ND	B	60h
HK	AR	B	-	-	+	ND	B	150h
Prekallikrein	AR	B	-	-	+	ND	B	35h
FXIII	AR	2-5%	+/-	-	-	1 in 2,000,000	Cryoprecipitate	11-14d

Note: (+): normal range values, (-): long range values, HK: high molecular weight kininogen, AR: autosomal recessive, aPTT: activated relative thromboplastin time, PT: prothrombin time, TT: thrombin time, ND: unknown, FFP: fresh frozen plasma, PCC: prothrombin complex concentrate.

Source: Palta, et al 2014

Conclusion

The creation of a suitable and scientific literature review on coagulation factors was one of the main objectives of this study. The majority of clotting factors are zymogens, which are inactive precursors of proteolytic enzymes (Barnoyev, 2023). Each zymogen's activation is represented by appending the letter "a" to the Roman numeral that corresponds to that specific zymogen (Barnoyev, 2023). With the exception of factors III, IV, and VIII, the liver produces the majority of procoagulants and anticoagulants. These proteins can bind calcium and other divalent cations and take part in the clotting cascade because of a post-translational change (vitamin K dependent γ carboxylation of glutamic acid residues). Anticoagulation results from either vitamin K deficiency or the use of vitamin K antagonists, such as warfarin (Barnoyev, 2023).

Finally, this study indicated that Nomenclature of coagulation proteins is rather complex. The terms fibrinogen, prothrombin, tissue factor (TF), and calcium are the popular designations for the first four of the twelve factors that were initially identified (Barnoyev, 2023). Roman numbers have not been given to the more recently identified clotting factors, high-molecular-weight kininogen and prekallikrein. Because of their short-lived coagulant action in preserved blood, factors V and VIII are also known as the labile factors (Barnoyev, 2023).

References

- Barmore, W., Bajwa, T., & Burns, B. (2023). Biochemistry, clotting factors. In *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Barnoyev, S.S. (2023). *Coagulation System in Various Diseases*. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 26. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/issue/view/26>
- Barzian, V., & Rezvani, Z. (2023, November 10–16). *Bioinformatic analysis of GRIN2B gene and GluN2B protein mutations in autism spectrum disorder (ASD) disease*. In *Proceedings of the 7th International Congress on Biomedicine (ICB 2023)* (Conference presentation). University of Kashan, Tehran, Iran.
- Biron, C. A., et al. (1999). Preoperative screening for von Willebrand disease type 1: Low yield and limited ability to predict bleeding. *Journal of Laboratory and Clinical Medicine*, 134(5), 605–611. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2143\(99\)90100-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2143(99)90100-2)
- Bolton-Maggs, P. H. (1998). The management of factor XI deficiency. *Haemophilia*, 4, 683.

- Butenas, S., & Mann, K. G. (2015). The effect of corn trypsin inhibitor and inhibiting antibodies for FXIa and FXIIa on coagulation of plasma and whole blood: Comment. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 13(3), 487.
- Caldwell, S. H., Hoffman, M., Lisman, T., Macik, B. G., Northup, P. G., Reddy, K. R., & Tripodi, A. (2006). Coagulation disorders and hemostasis in liver disease: Pathophysiology and critical assessment of current management. *Hepatology*, 44(10), 39.
- Dall'Osso, C., Guella, I., Duga, S., Locatelli, N., Paraboschi, E., Spreafico, M., Afrasiabi, A., Pechlaner, C., Peyvandi, F., Tenchini, M., & Asselta, R. (2008). Molecular characterization of three novel splicing mutations causing factor V deficiency and analysis of the F5 gene splicing pattern. *Haematologica*, 93(10), 1505.
- Elyasi, H., Rahimi, H., & Kiani, A. (2018). A review of medicinal herbs capable of preventing blood coagulation and platelet aggregation. *Herbal Medicines Journal*, 2(4), 1.
- Fatafta, H., Samantray, S., Sayyed-Ahmad, A., Coskuner-Weber, O., & Strodel, B. (2021). Molecular simulations of IDPs: From ensemble generation to IDP interactions leading to disorder-to-order transitions. In *Progress in Molecular Biology and Translational Science* (Vol. 183, pp. 135–185). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.pmbts.2021.06.003>
- Franchini, M., & Mannucci, P. (2010). Inhibitors of propagation of coagulation (factors VIII, IX and XI): A review of current therapeutic practice. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*.
- Göbel, K., Eichler, S., Wiend, H., Chavakis, T., Kleinschnitz, C., & Sven, G. (2018). The coagulation factors fibrinogen, thrombin, and factor XII in inflammatory disorders: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 9, 1731. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2018.01731>
- Hall, J. E., & Guyton, A. C. (2010). *Textbook of medical physiology* (12th ed.) [E-text]. Saunders. Retrieved from https://archive.org/stream/guytonandhalltextbookofmedicalphysiology12thed_202004
- Hassanabadi, S. H., Vatandoost, J., & Moghadam, M. (2018). Study of propeptide mutation effect on the human factor IX expression. *Journal of Cell and Molecular Research*, 30(2).
- Homayounfar, H. (1996). Recent advances regarding platelets. *JIUMS*, 2(4), 285.
- Ichinose, A., Asahina, T., & Kobayashi, T. (2005). Congenital blood coagulation factor XIII deficiency and perinatal management. *Drug Target Insights*, 6, 541.
- Joseph, J. S., & Kini, R. M. (2004). *Snake venom prothrombin activators similar to blood coagulation factor Xa*. *Current Drug Targets – Cardiovascular & Haematological Disorders*, 4(4), 397–416. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568006043335781>
- Kalantarian, G., Tarkalki, A., Poor Kabireh, R., Sheikh, N., & Karimi, Z. (2015). Structural and functional investigation of activated form of blood coagulation factor X. *Unknown Journal*, 12(4), 7.
- Lau, H. K. (2003). The interaction between platelets and factor VII/VIIa. *Transfusion and Apheresis Science*, 28, 279.
- Mashayekhi, A., & Shahbazi, S. H. (2014). Evaluation of the association between FGBrs1800790 and plasma fibrinogen levels. *The Scientific Journal of Iranian Blood Transfusion Organization*, 11(1), 49.
- Minnema, M. C., Cate, H. van, & Hack, C. E. (1999). The role of factor XI in coagulation: A matter of revision. *Seminars in Thrombosis and Hemostasis*, 25, 419.
- Naderi, M., Imani, M., Eshghi, P., Dorgalaleh, A., Tabibian, S. H., Alizadeh, S. H., Sanei Moghaddam, E., & Miri Moghaddam, E. (2013). Factor XIII deficiency in Sistan and Baluchistan province. *The Scientific Journal of Iranian Blood Transfusion Organization (Khoon)*, 10(41), 282.

- Naderi, S., & Najj, T. (2017). Mechanism of blood coagulation. *Journal of Laboratory & Diagnosis*, 13. (No DOI found)
- Nelson, D., & Cox, M. (2005). *Lehninger principles of biochemistry*. Sara Tenny Publisher.
- Palta, S., Saroa, R., & Palta, A. (2014). Overview of the coagulation system. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*, 58(5), 515–523. doi:10.4103/0019-5049.144643
- Perry, D. J. (2002). Factor VII deficiency. *British Journal of Haematology*, 118, 689.
- Persson, E., Selander, M., Linse, S., Drakenberg, T., Ohlin, A. K., & Stenflo, J. (1989). Calcium binding to the isolated β -hydroxyaspartic acid-containing epidermal growth factor-like domain of bovine factor X. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 264(28), 16897.
- Roberts, H. R. (1993). *Molecular biology of Hemophilia B* [Plenary lecture]. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 70(01), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0038-1646151>
- Schenone, M., Furie, B. C., & Furie, B. (2004). The blood coagulation cascade. *Current Opinion in Hematology*, 11(4), 7.

